

TECHNOLOGICAL PROFICIENCY OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN THE LENS OF DIGITAL EDUCATION

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Technological Proficiency of Senior High School Students in the Lens of Digital Education

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Abstract

Technological proficiency is essential in this modern society. This study determined the personal performance rating in technological proficiency of grade 12 Senior High School students. A quantitative method engaging descriptive survey research design was utilized in this study with 37 Grade 12 Senior High School students who are enrolled in the General Academic Strand (GAS) strand as respondents. For the data analysis, this study utilized a weighted mean of the students' responses indicating their level of technological proficiency in (1) software skills, (2) web navigation skills, and (3) online security skills. Based on the findings, the student's personal technological proficiency level was categorized as developing, which implies that the learned skills of the students using technology in class are good but need to be enhanced. The significant result showed that the current level of technological proficiency of the students needs further skills-building and enhancement. Thus, it is recommended that a corresponding intervention, innovation in teaching strategy, and technological skills-building are necessary to enhance the technological proficiency of the students through the lens of digital education.

Keywords: *technological proficiency, digital education, intervention, teaching strategy*

Introduction

The development of technology has changed the education landscape in the modern day, posing both a challenge and an opportunity in the teaching-learning process (Hanimoğlu, 2018). According to the United Nations (2020), there is growing evidence that increasing access to the use of technology and services can lead to improved educational results. Due to increased access to devices, the Internet, online learning environments, and collaboration tools, digital technologies have been incorporated into education during the past few decades, transforming the context of teaching and learning (Selwyn et al., 2017). Traditional classroom instruction cannot provide greater student engagement and speedier assessments (Haleem et al., 2022; Szymkowiak et al., 2020). The impact of technology, through curriculum integration, has filled in this scenario by transforming the traditional learning settings into more dynamic and engaging ones. The researchers have seen a dramatic change in academic collaboration and communication since the advent of internet technologies. The digital revolution made it possible to have free access to information throughout the world.

With the abundance of ICT tools available in today's classrooms, nearly all educators have made great strides in incorporating digital technology to enhance students' access to knowledge and chances for cooperative learning (Alenezi et al., 2023). Technological proficiency is the capacity to use technology for efficient communication, information organization, high-quality product production, and cognitive skill development (Saad & Sankaran, 2020). For learners to succeed academically, it is essential to evaluate their technological competency and learning objectives (Panoy, 2022). Szymkowiak et al. (2020) investigated how technology affected curriculum delivery in the teaching-learning process among the Z generation learners. They argued that since members of the Z generation prefer to use contemporary technology to help and guide their learning, traditional methods of instruction are inappropriate for educating them. They can study at a pace that works for them through modern educational methods that include games, podcasts, mobile apps, and videos.

The assessment of students' technological aptitude is, therefore, essential for educational institutions since it forms the basis for the delivery and facilitation of the teaching-learning process (Panoy, 2022). This underscores the importance of technology as a necessary instrument for an academic institution to operate and thrive in this multimodal digital era (Mdhlalose & Mlambo, 2023). However, this posed various challenges to student's learning. Numerous studies were carried out to examine high school students' technological proficiency in the teaching-learning process (Abojon et al., 2023; Erdem et al., 2018; Saad & Sankaran, 2020). However, there is a noticeable lack of research on the technological ability of Senior High School students enrolled in the General Academic Strands, despite the extensive initiatives for digital education.

Thus, this dearth in literature has prompted the researchers to undertake this study which aims to determine the personal performance rating in technological proficiency of grade 12 General Academic Strand (GAS) students as a basis for the formulation of proposed interventions that will enhance their literacy in utilizing technology in their respective courses.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the personal performance rating in technological proficiency of grade 12 General Academic Strand (GAS) students in one of the public schools in Talisay City, Cebu as a basis for formulating proposed interventions. Specifically, this sought to provide answers to the following questions:

1. What is the personal performance rating of the students in technological proficiency in terms of:
 - 1.1. software skills;

- 1.2. web navigation skills; and
- 1.3. online security skills?
2. Based on the findings, what interventions can be proposed?

Literature Review

Being technologically literate has been crucial to modern education. Technology tools and equipment can be integrated with instruction and learning experiences to become technologically proficient. Experimentation must be incorporated into instructional methods, and readily available technology tools and equipment must be maintained (Saad & Sankaran, 2020). For instance, education must adjust to the impact that technology brings, converting conventional learning spaces into technology-driven learning environments, given how quickly technology is developing.

Wardoyo et al. (2021) discovered that students' technology knowledge had a favorable and significant effect on game-based learning in their study on the relationship between technological understanding, game-based learning, and students' achievements. They also stated that computer skills are necessary for technology-based learning paradigms; thus, teachers and students must have these skills for effective learning. To adapt to the constantly shifting needs of society, technology, and instruction must interplay in the teaching-learning process.

Rafi et al. (2019) conducted another critical study to better understand students' technological proficiency in using database resources and conducting online information searches, where they discovered a crucial connection between students' technical proficiency in using digital tools to access information and conducting network searches for improved social communication and educational goals. Constant exposure to digital technologies helps students become more proficient in using technology in learning.

Technological proficiency has been an essential factor in learning language studies in Vietnam. Huynh (2024) asserts that to guarantee that students can acquire and apply information and abilities in language studies related to interacting with technology, it is imperative to develop targeted strategies and programs. This calls for funding from technology businesses and educational institutions and investments in infrastructure, training, and support. However, Khurram's (2020) study, which examines the experiences of graduates in acquiring computing skills, found that most graduates acquired these skills through informal, self-taught, or work-related learning. This concept highlights the value of experiential learning by supporting the notion that technology abilities can sometimes be acquired outside of the classroom through exposure to various technological instruments rather than through a rigid curriculum.

From the viewpoint of the teachers, Catog (2023) also investigated the underlying determinants of the degree of technological competency. An improvement in school culture and technological proficiency will probably result in an improvement in teacher behavior. Only using technology to teach was found to have a significant impact on teacher behavior among those with technology proficiency. Professional collaboration and self-determination were found to have a substantial effect on the behavior of public elementary school teachers when it came to school culture (Catog, 2023). This gave school administrators a great chance to create professional development programs that emphasize improving teachers' technology proficiency, which makes them valuable resources for improving learners' technological ability as well.

Digital education has become a prominent focus of most education systems worldwide with the advent of modern education, which has seen a significant shift from chalk-to-keyboard instruction. Digital innovation may boost the economy, provide value for businesses, and help society by, for example, fostering inclusivity, lowering inequality, and creating jobs (Rodrigues et al., 2021). The rise of e-learning environments, or collaborative interactions utilized for knowledge acquisition within an online computer-mediated digital system, is one of the effects of digital education (IGI Global, 2016). Al-Abdullatif and Gameil (2021) discovered that students will accept and become more motivated to use digital technologies through the PBL approach because they are perceived as easy to use and valuable, which will help them complete their learning tasks. This study examines the effect of digital technology integration on students' academic performance through project-based learning in an e-learning environment.

The capabilities and effects of students' technological and informational literacy on their engagement in online learning activities for e-learning are determined by Setyoko et al. (2023). The study's findings indicate a close relationship between technology and information literacy. Because there is a positive correlation between students' technological and information literacy, students' literacy levels will rise as they become more proficient with the many technology tools at their disposal. Thus, technology helps learners become more proficient in reading, writing, speaking, and listening—all essential for understanding new ideas.

Another study has examined the role of students' achievement emotions and technological self-efficacy in predicting their technology acceptance. Wang et al. (2023) revealed that the respondents' adoption of technology was significantly influenced by their feelings of achievement and technological self-efficacy. Put differently, students' achievement emotions may serve as a significant predictor of their technology acceptance by uniquely explaining 75% of its variance. In comparison, their technological self-efficacy may serve as a significant predictor of their acceptance of technology by uniquely explaining 59% of its variance. This implies technology acceptance depends on several factors including perceived technological self-efficacy.

With the above-mentioned literature, this study aims to fill a gap by gathering the most relevant data and significant criteria of technological proficiency based on a review of scientific literature and efforts to incorporate them into a single evaluating instrument.

Methodology

Research Design

A quantitative, engaging descriptive survey research design was utilized in this paper to determine the personal performance ratings of students in terms of technological proficiency.

Respondents

The study's respondents were the Grade 12 General Academic Strand (GAS) students in one of the public schools in Talisay City, Cebu, in the school year 2024-2025. A simple random sampling with a set margin of error of 5 % was utilized. Out of the total population of 41, the identified number of respondents was 37.

Instrument

Data was gathered using a questionnaire developed by the researchers. The questionnaire was personally designed by the researchers, evaluated by professionals, and reviewed by academic peers to ensure its validity. The tool is presented into three components: student's software skills, web navigation skills, and online security skills. Each scale's score was calculated by adding and averaging the scores from each subscale. This was scaled to four levels. A score of (1) denotes novice, (2) suggests developing, (3) indicates proficient, and (4) indicates advanced.

Procedure

The data-gathering process follows a set of phases. First, the researchers submitted an official letter to the principal's office requesting permission to conduct the study. The researchers then administered the survey. After collecting the participant responses, the data were evaluated in the most accurate manner possible by obtaining the mean and degree of personal performance rating in technological proficiency of General Academic Strand students.

Ethical Considerations

Before the survey was conducted, the researchers obtained permission from the respondents by asking for their permission to participate in this research study with their full consent. As part of the survey process, respondents were adequately notified of their rights. Human privacy was respected during the interview process and data collection. The researchers protect the secrecy of the responses and the respondents' identities. Finally, the researchers assured that all research materials would be destroyed following the completion of the study.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of students' level of technological proficiency in terms of software skills, web navigational skills, and social security skills.

Table 1. Students level of technological proficiency in terms of software skills

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
I can prepare and give presentations using PowerPoint, Google Slides, Prezi, etc.	1.95	Developing
I can utilize Canva and other editing apps in making and submitting my learning task.	2.37	Developing
I can work collaboratively on a shared online document using Google Docs, Google Slides, etc.	2.20	Developing
I can create a report using Excel and spreadsheets for my assigned learning tasks.	1.91	Developing
I can compose my assignments and other learning tasks using Microsoft Word, Google Docs, etc.	2.42	Developing
Total Mean	2.31	Developing

Table 1 presents the students' level of technological proficiency in terms of software skills. The grand mean of the five indicators, as shown in the table, is 2.31, which falls under the developing level. The table shows that all five indicators fall under the developing level. The statement "I can compose my assignments and other learning tasks using Microsoft Word, Google Docs, etc." got the highest mean of 2.42, followed by the statement "I can utilize Canva and other editing apps in making and submitting my learning task" which garnered a 2.37 mean score. "I can work collaboratively on a shared online document using Google Docs, Google Slides, etc." got a mean of 2.20. At the same time "I can prepare and give presentations using PowerPoint, Google Slides, Prezi, etc." statement got a mean of 1.95. Among the five indicators, the statement "I can create a report using Excel and spreadsheets for my assigned learning tasks" got the lowest mean score of 1.91 which has an interpretation of development.

Based on the results, the respondents have a developing level of proficiency in using Microsoft Excel and spreadsheets which means that their skills still need to be enhanced. These days, students need to be proficient in Microsoft Excel to vary their skill set and improve their chances of landing a job (Abd Hadi et al., 2021). It is true that for students to succeed in this rapidly evolving technology society, being able to use this application is a necessary ability. Students need to be directed in the educational landscape to be able to think critically and evaluate how they use technology to support their academic responsibilities (Julia & Isrokatun, 2019) for these are essentials for them to succeed in today's digital world. Furthermore, Rodrigues et al. (2021) agreed that the ability to use such emerging digital technologies in a critical, cooperative, and inventive manner is a necessary component of digital competency.

Table 2. *Students level of technological proficiency in terms of web navigation skills*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
I can navigate and conduct research using Google Scholar and other online search engines.	3.01	Proficient
I can easily find primary sources of information for my learning task.	2.45	Developing
I can keep track of the sites and information I have searched using online bookmarks.	1.75	Developing
I can recognize false information available online.	2.39	Developing
I can identify if a website is safe to navigate or not.	2.36	Developing
Total Mean	1.99	Developing

Table 2 presents the students' level of technological proficiency in web navigation skills. The grand mean of the five indicators, as shown in the table, is 1.99, which falls to the developing level. Data in the table reveal that four indicators fall under the developing level while one falls under the proficient level. The statement "I can navigate and conduct research using Google Scholar and other online search engines." got the highest mean of 3.01 with an interpretation of proficient, followed by the statement "I can easily find primary sources of information for my learning task." which garnered a 2.45 mean. "I can recognize false information available online." got a mean of 2.39, while the "I can identify if a website is safe to navigate or not." statement got a mean of 2.36. Among the five indicators, the statement "I can keep track of the sites and information I have searched using online bookmarks." got the lowest mean of 1.75 which has an interpretation of developing.

Based on the results, students have the lowest proficiency in tracking the sites and information searched using online bookmarks. This finding implies that their technological skills in this specific area need further enhancement. In a related study, Miliou & Angeli (2021) discovered that Gen Z students' technology use is limited and may not adequately cover the knowledge and abilities required to carry out internet-related tasks in higher education. This limitation posed a challenge in the learning performance among students especially in today's modern world. Research indicates that although these children were born into a digital age, they still need to learn how to use new technology the same way as they would any other new skill (Wen & Walters, 2022).

However, respondents have indicated a proficient level of technological proficiency in navigating and conducting research using Google Scholar and other online search engines. Undoubtedly, the emergence of Google Scholar and other innovations in library systems that offer global access to information has signified the end of the academic library as an institution constrained by its four walls (Oh & Colón-Aguirre, 2019). Students were consistently exposed to these search engines which they perceived as relevant, widely accessible, and offered access to all the information they could require for their field of study (Alotaibi & Johnson, 2020). Consistent utilization and exposure to online search engines like Google Scholar enhance students' skills in navigating these platforms and are a significant predictor of the research skills possessed by students (Adedeji, 2023).

Table 3. *Students level of technological proficiency in terms of online security skills*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
I am fully aware of the risk of spam and phishing attempts when utilizing social media	1.72	Novice
I always reconsider the pros and cons before joining as a participating member of an online community.	2.29	Developing
I am knowledgeable about the ambiguous copyright and intellectual property issues rampant in social media.	1.63	Novice
I conduct fact-checking on the information I share on social media.	1.70	Novice
I always make sure that my post online will not go against the community guidelines.	2.11	Developing
Total Mean	1.95	Developing

Table 3 presents the students' level of technological proficiency in terms of online security skills. The grand mean of the five indicators, as shown in the table, is 1.95, which falls to the developing level. The table has shown that two indicators fall under the developing level while three indicators fall under the novice level. The statement "I always reconsider the pros and cons before joining as a participating member of an online community." got the highest mean of 2.29, followed by the statement "I always make sure that my post online will not go against the community guidelines." which garnered a 2.11 mean. "I am fully aware of the risk of spam and phishing attempts when utilizing social media." statement got a mean of 1.72. At the same time, the statement "I conduct fact-checking on the information I share on social media." got a mean of 1.70. Among the five indicators, the statement "I am knowledgeable about the ambiguous copyright and intellectual property issues rampant in social media." garnered the lowest mean of 1.63, which falls under the novice level.

Based on the findings, students have indicated a developing level in reconsidering the pros and cons of joining an online community and got the highest mean among the five indicators. Although this skill still needs to be enhanced, students demonstrated a high degree of proficiency based from the mean of assessing online groups before joining, which is an essential aspect of digital literacy. Since digital literacy makes it easier to obtain information and is one of the most important defenses against the growing number of e-threats (Tomczyk, 2019), students must possess the necessary knowledge and abilities for online security. Furthermore, as more people utilize the Internet, there is a greater need to educate consumers about the risks, assaults, and privacy concerns associated with it (Jain et al., 2021).

Conclusions

Based on the result of this study, the researchers conclude that the students' technological proficiency level is categorized as developing, which implies that the learned skills of the students using technology in class need to be enhanced. The software skills, web navigation skills, and social security skills show a significant result that the student's performance rating in technological proficiency is categorized as developing but needs further technological skills-building to ensure the total implementation in the integration of the technology and curriculum in the class. The student's current level of technological proficiency needs to be enhanced in line with the 21st-century learning trend. Thus, a corresponding intervention, innovation in teaching strategy, and technological skills-building are necessary to improve the technological proficiency of students and enable them to be equipped with the necessary technological skills through the lens of digital education.

References

- Abd Hadi, A. A., Hashim, H. S., Salim, S., Yahaya, N. A., & Kadri, M. a. M. (2021). Student's perception of the use of excel spreadsheet in financial reporting. In 3rd International Conference on Business Studies and Education (ICBE) 28 & 29 March 2021. Retrieved from <https://www.icbe.my/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/FULLMANUSCRIPTMARCH2021.pdf#page=30>
- Abojon , J. A., Derasin, L. C., Canque, M. S., Cordero, L. S., & Trinidad, G. A. (2023). Technological skills of senior high school students in state-run basic education institutions in the Philippines. *European Chemical Bulletin*, pp. 12510-12518. Retrieved from https://www.scihorizon.com/cdn/pdf/1685357340_a201a0c49032731586c4.pdf
- Adedeji, A. A. (2023). Use of search engines as predictors of research skills of postgraduate students in library schools: A case study of south-west, Nigeria. In *Library Philosophy and Practice (E-journal)*. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/7893>
- Alenezi, M., Wardat, S., & Akour, M. (2023). The need of integrating digital education in higher education: Challenges and Opportunities. *Sustainability*, 15(6), 4782. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15064782>
- Alotaibi, F., & Johnson, F. (2020). Why we like Google Scholar: Postgraduate students' perceptions of factors influencing their intention to use. *Aslib Journal of Information Management*, 72(4), 587–603. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ajim-10-2019-0304>
- Al-Abdullatif, A. M., & Gameil, A. A. (2021). The effect of digital technology integration on students' academic performance through project-based learning in an e-learning environment. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning/International Journal: Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 16(11), 189. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v16i11.19421>
- Catog, M. U. (2023). Technology proficiency and school culture as the influence of teaching behavior among public elementary school teachers. *East Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(4), 1481–1498. <https://doi.org/10.55927/eajmr.v2i4.3748>
- Erdem, A., Uzal, G., & Saka, M. (2018). High school students' proficiency perceptions to the usage of technology products at physics lessons. *The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 17(2), 55–67. <http://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1176164.pdf>
- Haleem, A., Javaid, M., Qadri, M. A., & Suman, R. (2022). Understanding the role of digital technologies in education: A review. *Sustainable Operations and Computers*, 3, 275–285. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.susoc.2022.05.004>
- Hanmoğlu, E. (2018). The impact technology has had on high school education over the years. *World Journal of Education*, 8(6), 96. <https://doi.org/10.5430/wje.v8n6p96>
- Huynh, M. T. (2024). Developing and enhancing technological proficiency for university students: Opportunities and challenges. *Educational Administration: Theory and Practice*, 30–4, 806–812. <https://doi.org/10.53555/kuey.v30i4.1570>
- IGI Global (2016). What is e-learning environment. Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/mprzv28c>
- Jain, A. K., Sahoo, S. R., & Kaubiyal, J. (2021). Online social networks security and privacy: Comprehensive review and analysis. *Complex & Intelligent Systems*, 7(5), 2157–2177. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40747-021-00409-7>
- Julia, J., & Isrokatur, I. (2019). Technology literacy and student practice: Lecturing critical evaluation skills. *International Journal of Learning Teaching and Educational Research*, 18(9), 114–130. <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.18.9.6>
- Khurram, M. (2020). Perceptions and expectations of the technological proficiency levels of university business school graduates: Representations of graduates and employers. Doctoral dissertation, Memorial University of Newfoundland. Retrieved from <https://research.library.mun.ca/14614/>
- Mdhlalose, D., & Mlambo, G. (2023). Integration of technology in education and its impact on learning and teaching. *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies*, 47(2), 54–63. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajess/2023/v47i21021>
- Miliou, O., & Angeli, C. (2021). Measuring the internet skills of Gen Z students in higher education: Validation of the internet skills scale in university settings. In 7th International Conference on Higher Education Advances (HEAd'21) (pp. 1359-1368). Editorial Universitat Politècnica de València.

- Oh, K. E., & Colón-Aguirre, M. (2019). A comparative study of perceptions and use of Google Scholar and academic library discovery systems. *College & Research Libraries*, 876–878. Retrieved from <https://thescholarship.ecu.edu/items/3f25041c-9f81-4500-9124-0fdcae1da9a5>
- Panoy, J. F. D., Andrade, R. R., Febrer, L. B., & Ching, D. A. (2022). Perceived proficiency with technology and online learning expectations of students in the graduate program of one state university in the Philippines. *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, 12(7), 615–624. <https://doi.org/10.18178/ijiet.2022.12.7.1661>
- Rafi, M., JianMing, Z., & Ahmad, K. (2019). Technology integration for students' information and digital literacy education in academic libraries. *Information Discovery and Delivery*, 47(4), 203–217. <https://doi.org/10.1108/idd-07-2019-0049>
- Rodrigues, A. L., Cerdeira, L., De Lourdes Machado-Taylor, M., & Alves, H. (2021). Technological skills in higher education—different needs and different uses. *Education Sciences*, 11(7), 326. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci11070326>
- Saad, N., & Sankaran, S. (2020). Technology proficiency in teaching and facilitating. *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acrefore/9780190264093.013.591>
- Selwyn, N., Nemorin, S., Bulfin, S., & Johnson, N. F. (2017). Left to their own devices: The everyday realities of one-to-one classrooms. *Oxford Review of Education*, 43(3), 289–310. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03054985.2017.1305047>
- Setyoko, S., Yani, A. F. S., Fitria, D., & Suryanti, S. (2023). Analysis of college student technology literacy and information literacy skills: E-learning activities based on online platforms in higher education. *Jurnal Penelitian Pendidikan IPA*, 9(11), 9416–9422. <https://doi.org/10.29303/jppipa.v9i11.5276>
- Szymkowiak, A., Melović, B., Dabić, M., Jeganathan, K., & Kundi, G. S. (2021). Information technology and Gen Z: The role of teachers, the internet, and technology in the education of young people. *Technology in Society*, 65, 101565. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2021.101565>
- Tomczyk, U. (2019). Skills in the area of digital safety as a key component of digital literacy among teachers. *Education and Information Technologies*, 25(1), 471–486. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-019-09980-6>
- United Nation. (2020). The Impact of Digital Technologies. Retrieved July 1, 2024, from <https://www.un.org/en/un75/impact-digital-technologies>
- Wang, Y., Wang, Y., Pan, Z., & Ortega-Martín, J. L. (2023). The predicting role of EFL students' achievement emotions and technological self-efficacy in their technology acceptance. *the Asia-Pacific Education Researcher*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40299-023-00750-0>
- Wardoyo, C., Satrio, Y. D., Narmaditya, B. S., & Wibowo, A. (2021). Do technological knowledge and game-based learning promote students achievement: A lesson from Indonesia. *Heliyon*, 7(11). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e08467>
- Wen, X., & Walters, S. M. (2022). The impact of technology on students' writing performances in elementary classrooms: A meta-analysis. *Computers and Education Open*, 3, 100082. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeo.2022.100082>

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